

D8.1 LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination Reports

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Executive summary

The present document presents and details the LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination plans (PCP and PDP), aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. EUT is responsible for designing and implementing LIFE PRISTINE communication and dissemination strategy through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

The channels and platforms considered in the communication and dissemination plan are the official website, social media channels, materials to be distributed in key events, media relations to specialised and general media outlets, scientific publications, the organisation of engagement activities and attendance on strategic conferences, fairs and congresses where the project can be presented, among others.

This deliverable also details the target groups, key messages, communication and dissemination activities planned, requirements and the process of reporting and monitoring communication activities.

In addition, the document reports on the communication and dissemination actions carried out by partners during the first six months of the project and upcoming activities. This report will be periodically updated, reflecting the communication and dissemination activities carried out by partners according to the communication and dissemination KPIs measured.

[NOTE: Front page and Executive summary will be published in the website for all deliverables]

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACC	ACCIONA
CEC	Contaminants of Emerging Concern
DW	Drinking water
EC	European Commission
ESAMUR	Entidad de Saneamiento y Depuración de la Región de Murcia
EUT	Fundació Eurecat
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LR	Layman's Report
NXF	NX Filtration
PCP	PRISTINE Communication Plan
PDP	PRISTINE Dissemination Plan
VCI	Visual Corporate Identity
WP	Work Package
WW	Wastewater
XYL	Xylem

Introduction

LIFE PRISTINE is a four-year project aiming to develop the PRISTINE Integrated Solution to **remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams**. The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be adaptable on a case-by-case basis for drinking water (DW), to protect humans from CECs, and for wastewater (WW), to protect the environment and remove these contaminants from the water cycle.

In opposition to other existing technologies, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution will permanently remove CECs from water, thus directly applying Zero Waste and Circular Economy principles and coming ahead of existing and near future CECs regulations.

EUT is the leader of **WP8 - Communication & Raise Awareness**, including three tasks: **Task 8.1. Communication and dissemination plan**, **Task 8.2. Communication activities** and **Task 8.3. Networking activities**

The LIFE PRISTINE Dissemination and Communication Plans have the objectives of (i) raising awareness on the project main goals and results, (ii) divulging the project outcomes to as the broadest audience possible, (iii) sharing the know-how generated from the project to the scientific and industrial community and supporting all project activities training the next generation of researchers and industry professionals and (iv) disseminating the project results and activities to ensure market uptake.

This document compiles the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, including the creation and maintenance of the project's website, social media posts, the creation of promotional materials, media relations, scientific publications, the organization of workshops, training activities, stakeholder engagement events and attendance to strategic conferences, fairs, congresses and other key events.

Regarding communication and dissemination, the deliverable also includes the objectives, key messages, target audiences and timing of the different activities. Key performance indicators (KPIs) for each communication and dissemination action have been defined and will be reported, ensuring the traceability of the activities that are not listed under particular deliverables or milestones.

All the actions in the plan consider the European Commission's requirements for funding recognition, as well as the recommendations and guidelines for communication and dissemination of LIFE programme projects¹.

¹ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/communication-and-gdpr-rules_en

1 Distribution of responsibilities

The LIFE PRISTINE dissemination and communication strategy foresees the active involvement and commitment of all project partners for presenting the project and its main outcomes.

WP8 Communication & Raise awareness includes the following tasks related to communication and dissemination tasks with the following objectives:

- **Task 8.1 Communication and dissemination plan (M1-M6)**
 - Development of LIFE PRISTINE Communication Plan (PCP) and Dissemination Plan (PDP)
- **Task 8.2 Communication activities (M1-M48)**
 - Set up LIFE PRISTINE communication channels
 - Generate awareness on the project, its findings and economic / environmental impact
 - Inform and promote project activities and results to broad audiences
 - Support project exploitation and results' market uptake
 - Transfer knowledge and results to the industrial and scientific community
- **Task 8.3 Networking activities**
 - Ensure wide and transversal dissemination of project activities
 - Organisation of project meetings, technical forums/workshops and conferences

EUT is the Communication and Dissemination lead beneficiary, responsible for coordinating WP8 activities, ensuring the proper information exchange within the consortium and supporting the full communication and dissemination of the project and its results.

All partners will contribute to ensure the successful implementation of the communication and dissemination activities and the reach to the different stakeholder groups identified.

2 Requirements

All communication and dissemination materials produced in the project (posters, presentations, promotional materials, publications, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format will display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement.

According to the Grant Agreement *“unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:*

- a) *Display the EU emblem*
- b) *Include the following text*

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 1. Funding acknowledgement

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Additionally, according to the Grant Agreement, *Communication activities and infrastructure, equipment or major results funded by the grant must moreover display the LIFE Programme logo:*

Figure 2. LIFE Programme flag

3 Communication and Dissemination plans

The main goals behind LIFE PRISTINE Communication (PCP) and Dissemination Plan (PDP) are:

- **Raise awareness** on Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs), water technologies and the PRISTINE solution to permanently eliminating the compounds present in the water environment.
- Identify the project audience groups in terms of communication and dissemination activities, as well as the **main means and channels** that will be used to make the project known to general public.
- **Support the exploitation** of project results and market uptake.
- **Share the know-how generated** from the project to the scientific and industrial community.
- **Establish a fluid two-way communication** to get real feedback on the competitiveness of the results.

It is worth noting that, in order to protect the commercial interests of the partners, the publication of the materials will be carried out under the principle of as 'widely publicly available as possible, but as confidential as necessary', except for submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners will decide which part of the projects' information is to be protected by copyright or IP protection measures and which part of the above information is suitable for a wide dissemination.

3.1 Target of communication and dissemination

An initial analysis of the dissemination target audiences has been done. Four stakeholder groups have been identified as target audience of the communication and dissemination activities, including: academia, industrial community, policy makers and the society at large. Detailed information is presented in Figure 1.

Scientific and academic community

- Universities, research & technology organisations researching in water pollution, emerging contaminants, encapsulated adsorbents, advanced oxidation processes, membrane technologies and artificial intelligence based sensors
- Scientific associated media
- Attendees to trade exhibitions covering the project's fields (Stockholm Water Week, Singapore Water Week, Aquatec Amsterdam, WEFTEC Chicago, IEEEXpo Shanghai, IFAT München, AMTA, etc.)

Industry, end users and customers

- Water sector, including water treatment plant operators and owners
- Industries in which the PRISTINE outcomes can be transferred or replicated (i.e. agri-food sector)
- Technology developers and providers, including the monitoring industry

Policy actors and decision makers

- Governmental bodies in charge of resources management (e.g. Departments of Environment)
- Networks associations (AWT, IWA, AEAS, etc.)
- Policy makers
- Decision makers
- Standardisation bodies and technical committees

Society at large

- General public and mass media
- EU citizens
- NGOs

Figure 3. LIFE PRISTINE stakeholders groups

3.2 Channels

For communication and dissemination activities, the LIFE PRISTINE project will use a wide range of channels and actions, ranging from social media activity, media relations, promotional materials to scientific publications, organisation of workshops and specific stakeholder engagement events, and presentation of the project in key events.

Figure 4. LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination Channels / Activities

Besides the aforementioned project channels, all partners will make use of their own channels (websites, presence on social media and corporate newsletters / publications) to disseminate news about LIFE PRISTINE and reach a broader audience.

3.3 Key messages

The communication and dissemination plans' messages have been carefully designed and tailored to every stakeholder involved and will be adapted to the different LIFE PRISTINE communication and dissemination channels. The messages are aligned with the main dissemination and communication objectives and convey the possibilities and strength of the demonstration done during the project's execution.

The following messages will be evolved in pertinent tailored messages for all audiences, both specialised and non-specialised, so the objectives and outcomes of LIFE PRISTINE can be widely spread and understood, being those key ones:

- LIFE PRISTINE faces the challenge of water scarcity, affecting more than 2.8 billion people around the world.
- The LIFE PRISTINE Solution, integrated and versatile, consists of a synergistical combination of individual water technologies.
- LIFE PRISTINE will focus on perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), pesticides, pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs), toxins, antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) and microplastics as the main families of emerging contaminants.

- The PRISTINE Solution is based on technologies known in the water sector, based on adsorption, nanofiltration and advanced oxidation processes, that are the starting point for the development of the Solution.
- In opposition to other existing technologies, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution will permanently remove CECs from water, thus directly applying Zero Waste and Circular Economy principles and coming ahead of existing and near future CECs regulations.
- The PRISTINE Solution aims to eliminate more than 80% of emerging pollutants found in the project, going beyond the limits established by the Directive on the quality of water intended for human consumption (Directive 2020 /2184/CE) and the European regulation regarding the minimum requirements for the reuse of water (Regulation (EU) 2020/741).
- LIFE PRISTINE considers two demo scenarios in order to demonstrate the versatility of the Solution. Firstly, its effectiveness will be demonstrated in a Wastewater Treatment Plant in Murcia and then installed at the Bilbao Bizkaia Advanced Water Treatment Center (CATABB).
- LIFE PRISTINE is a project funded by the LIFE Programme of the European Commission, under the LIFE Programme, to eliminate emerging pollutants from the integral water cycle.
- The project has a duration of 48 months and a budget of 3.764.689,07€.

4 PRISTINE Communication Plan (PCP)

The following sections include a list of the different communication activities, tools and actions planned for the LIFE PRISTINE project (Corporate Visual Identity, website, promotional materials, social media, press releases, etc.).

All the communication actions and channels planned will be continuously aligned with the dissemination of the activities and project's results and will follow the calendar of the project's execution and its milestones and achievements.

4.1 Project Visual Corporate Identity and templates

According to the work plan, EUT is responsible for designing LIFE PRISTINE's official Visual Corporate Identity (VCI), aimed at **properly aligning all communication materials across all the tasks of the project.**

The Visual Corporate Identity is essential to create and establish LIFE PRISTINE's identity, as well as to provide a coherent and consistent image of the project. It is important to **use the elements established in the VCI manual properly and only employ the authorised documents templates to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand and do it consistently.**

The following sections describe the different materials and elements designed, including the project's logo, templates, colours, fonts and graphic elements to be used and implemented in all communication and dissemination actions by all project's partners.

4.1.1 LIFE PRISTINE logo

The logo is the main brand element of the visual identity of LIFE PRISTINE and has the objective to represent the different concepts surrounding the project.

As pictured in the following figures, the LIFE PRISTINE logo includes the name of the project and the colours established in the corporate visual identity manual: turquoise and navy blue. These colours enable a quick comprehension of the project's field: water cleanliness.

Three different versions of the logo have been created: a full colour logo, and positive and negative black and white logo.

Figure 5. Full colour logo

Figure 6. Black and white logo positive

Figure 7. Black and white logo negative

4.1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards guidebook have been produced and distributed among partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised, and all partners use the elements properly in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand.

The visual identity manual defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to LIFE PRISTINE, including logos, colours, fonts, etc. Partners should treat the guidebook as a source of the materials and instructions and as a basis for further development of project materials.

The sections hereinafter include and describe some parts of the manual.

4.1.2.1 Corporate colours

This section presents the LIFE PRISTINE colours palette that must be used in all project materials, such as the website, social media and other promotional and graphic resources.

According to the palette designed, the main colours of the LIFE PRISTINE project are turquoise (Pantone: 7473 C) and navy blue (Pantone: 2746 C). On the other hand, a gradient combination between the two main colours is allowed.

All LIFE PRISTINE colours are allowed to use with no hierarchy.

Figure 8. LIFE PRISTINE project colours

4.1.2.2 Fonts

The Visual Corporate Image manual establishes two types of fonts to be used for project documents and materials.

Foundry Sterling will be the special font used for promotional and advertising materials. This type of font and its different versions are free, and partners can download it in Google Fonts page. The text font for the headings will be Foundry Sterling Extra Bold, while for the texts we will use Foundry Sterling Book.

**Foundry sterling extrabold:
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890**

Figure 9. Use of font for promotional materials

On the other hand, Trebuchet MS is the main font established for deliverables and internal documents because it is a standard Microsoft Office included in Word and PowerPoint documents, among others.

Trebuchet regular:
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Trebuchet regular italic:
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Trebuchet bold:
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Trebuchet bold italic:
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Figure 10. Use of fonts for deliverables and internal documents

4.1.3 Templates

Communication Leader EUT has prepared different document templates, which have been shared with all partners. A PowerPoint template has been produced for internal and external presentations, as well as four different Word documents: one for deliverables, one for meeting’s agenda, one for letters or other purposes and another one to be used for meeting minutes.

These template materials will be used throughout all the project’s execution to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

4.1.3.1 Template for deliverables

A Word document template has been created and shared with partners to be used for all project’s deliverables.

This template establishes the use of a page header with the project’s logo, the funding body’s logo and the project’s claim and reference, and a footer with some information about the document and a graphic element created for project materials.

Normal Text is ARIAL 11pt, single line spacing and justified.
Each section has to start at a new page.

Title 1 is the Section Heading.

Titles (2-6) are the Numbered Subsections* (examples in page 10)

Template for unordered lists: *(examples in page 10)

- Style bulleted - To be used with bullets (unordered lists). Don't change the bullets unless absolutely necessary
 - Style bulleted - 2nd Level of bullets
 - Style bulleted - 3rd Level of bullets

It's important to have a template for ordered lists too: *(examples in page 10)

1. The style is called Numbered bullet and it follows the same rules as the unordered list.
 - i. The 2nd Level of the ordered list uses Latin numbering.
 - a. The 3rd Level of the ordered list uses the alphabet.

Figure 11. LIFE PRISTINE deliverable template

4.1.3.2 Template for agenda

The template designed for the agenda presents a header page with the LIFE PRISTINE and funding body’s logos and a footer with some information and a graphic element that symbolises the sun also included in the project’s logo.

The font used for title in agenda’s document are **Trebuchet MS 18pt, bold** and in turquoise colour and for the normal text is also **Trebuchet MS 10,5pt, single line spacing.**

Figure 12. LIFE PRISTINE agenda template

4.1.3.3 Template for letter

This template is specifically designed for letters that consortium partners may need to write during the project. It includes some lines for the details of the sender and reference to LIFE PRISTINE project. Text is **Trebuchet MS 11pt**

Figure 13. LIFE PRISTINE letter template

4.1.3.4 Template for minutes

This template will be used to present the minutes and the list of attendants to an internal project meeting. The document includes a header page with the LIFE PRISTINE and funding body’s logos and a footer with some information and a graphic element.

The font applied for the text is **Trebuchet MS 12pt and 11pt.**

Figure 14. LIFE PRISTINE's meeting minutes template

4.1.3.5 PowerPoint presentation template

A Powerpoint template has been designed to be used for all project’s internal and external presentations.

This document presents a variety of slides with different options to include the text and different visual elements to be used and adapted by all partners when preparing an internal project’s presentation.

A screenshot of some slides is shown below:

Figure 15. View of LIFE PRISTINE presentation template

4.2 Website

All information regarding LIFE PRISTINE public website is detailed in deliverable **D8.2 LIFE PRISTINE website**.

4.3 Social media

EUT manages LIFE PRISTINE’s social media accounts and its content. LIFE PRISTINE project will count usage of a **Twitter Channel**, ([@PRISTINE_EU](#)), a LinkedIn channel ([LIFE PRISTINE](#)) and a **YouTube channel** ([LIFE PRISTINE](#)).

On the other hand, **partners will contribute to spreading the word on their corporate and personal social media channels**, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube or Instagram.

The project coordinator will be in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels and, whenever possible, will promote the use of social media complicities between LIFE PRISTINE and its sister projects.

4.3.1 Twitter

Figure 16. View of Twitter profile

Twitter is the 2.0 tool most used by the European Commission to now disseminate the LIFE programme, so the creation of an account has full meaning. The account will be managed by EUT with the support of project partners for the correct management of the account.

LIFE PRISTINE project’s main objective on Twitter is to raise awareness on CECs and water technologies, as well as promoting the benefits of the project’s solution.

Twitter will also be used to connect with EU institutions and related projects. Twitter allows us to reach directly targeted audiences from validated professional accounts.

4.3.1.1 Account management

EUT has created a **regular content plan** to be disseminated through the LIFE PRISTINE Twitter account. All consortium partners can propose content (text, images, videos...) to be distributed in this channel and can spread the word through their own social media channels by sharing and engaging with the content.

A Hootsuite account, a tool facilitating the publication of content and activity monitoring, has been created for scheduling tweets and shortening URLs. Comments and answers will be managed manually, to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

4.3.1.2 Content strategy

When creating and publishing content about the project, EUT and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations in order to maximise the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise LIFE PRISTINE's project impact and encourages market uptake to secure a critical mass of early adopters.

- **Disseminating project activities:** sharing information on project events, milestones, developments accomplished, and other dissemination activities organised by the project, including text and photos if possible.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on water technologies, emerging contaminants, water scarcity, water regulation, innovative solutions for water filtration, etc.
- **Disseminating audio-visual and promotional materials produced** to make the project more accessible/understandable.
- **Sharing news and articles published on the website** to increase traffic.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, the frequent use of the following hashtags is proposed:
 - **Project:** #LIFEPRISTINE #PRISTINE #PRISTINEProject #PRISTINEIntegratedSolution #LIFEProgramme #EUProjects
 - **Project topics:** #WaterTechnologies #ContaminantsOfEmergingConcern #CECs #Water #WaterScarcity #CleanWater #ODS #DrinkingWater #Wastewater #DW #WW #CircularEconomy #AdsorbingCapsules #EncapsulatedAdsorbents #Nanofiltration #AOP #UV #LED #AI #ArtificialIntelligence #PFAs #PPCPs
- Project partners (@ACCIONA, @Eurecat_News, @Esamur_Aguas, @NXFiltration and @Xylem) will be mentioned when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.
- Accounts and content from projects funded under the similar topic will also be mentioned and retweeted.

4.3.1.3 Branding strategy

- Twitter posts will be prepared covering fairs, trade shows, congresses and other events where LIFE PRISTINE participates, using the official hashtag of the event.
- The official LIFE PRISTINE Twitter account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project

4.3.1.4 Influencers strategy

- Regularly mention @LIFE_programme @EU_ENV @EUClimateAction @EU_Comission @cinea_eu @EUEnvironment @EurEau @IWAHQ @EUgreenresearch in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Identify and mention influencers in the field of water technology, encapsulation technologies, AOP processes, contaminants of emerging concern...
- Identify and mention the accounts of specialized magazines and tag them once specific results of LIFE PRISTINE project are published (e.g. Environmental Science & Technology @EnvSciTech, Journal of Hazardous Materials @HAZMAT_journal, etc.)
- Identification of stakeholder's accounts to promote follow-back and to increase the number of LIFE PRISTINE followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

4.3.1.5 Followers and following

Our reputation on Twitter depends on the number of users we follow. There must be a balanced number between our followers and the users we follow. Otherwise, it is considered that the tool is being misused, since the objective is to share knowledge bidirectionally.

Therefore, LIFE PRISTINE will follow people and organisations related to the project's topic. At the first stage of the project, LIFE PRISTINE's Twitter account will follow all project partners, as well as institutions, centres and professionals in the field of the project. The social media accounts, as well as the Twitter profiles of reference covering the project topic will also be followed.

We will avoid followers with an offensive avatar (for example, pornographic, racist) or spammers, which we will block.

4.3.1.6 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated in order to measure Twitter's KPIs (please view Communication KPIs section for more information) and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

At M5, the LIFE PRISTINE Twitter has **19 followers, 11 tweets published and 1,301 impressions**. (Data Analytics from October 2022 - M3 until December 2022 - M5).

4.3.1.6.1 *First battery of tweets*

See below the **first battery of tweets** proposed to be published in the months of October-December, with the main objective to **bring traffic to the website** and **promote the project's main concepts**. The twitter posts are in line with the key messages to be targeted to the main stakeholder groups.

New batteries for Twitter will be prepared periodically to inform about the project developments.

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Oct 26 ...

📌 The #LIFEPRISTINE project has started!

Follow us to discover our progress towards effectively removing Contaminants of Emerging Concern #CECs in water treatment systems thanks to the #PRISTINE Integrated Solution 💧

More news to come soon...

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Nov 4 ...

The #LIFEPRISTINE project aims to develop the PRISTINE Integrated Solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern #CECs from water streams

💡 This solution will be adaptable for drinking #water, to protect humans from CECs, and for wastewater, to protect the environment

ACCIONA and 8 others

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Nov 15 ...
 The #PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be demonstrated in two operationally representative scenarios ✓

- ◆ Drinking water in the Bilbao Bizkaia Advanced Water Treatment Centre #CATABB
- ◆ Wastewater in a Wastewater Treatment Plant #WWTP in Murcia

eurecat.org/en/portfolio-i...

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Nov 22 ...
 The #LIFEPRISTINE project has been presented at the 3rd Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals #YWP #IWA 2022 by M^a del Mar Micó, partner from @ACCIONA

She focused on the project objectives, technology and demonstration scenarios #cleanwater

eurecat.org/en/portfolio-i...

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Nov 24 ...
 In this interview, Ana Jiménez-Banzo, project coordinator from #LIFEPRISTINE, discusses our objectives and the development of the #PRISTINE Integrated Solution for the removal of #CECs in water streams

Read it to know more about us! 📌

[aguasresiduales.info](#) @aguasresiduales · Nov 23
 #ENTREVISTA
 Conocemos el proyecto sobre contaminantes de preocupación emergente, LIFE PRISTINE con su coordinadora, Ana Jiménez-Banzo.
 @ACCIONA
aguasresiduales.info/revista/entrev...

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Dec 13 ...
 Want to know more about the #PRISTINE project?

Join our community of interest and keep up to date on our advances towards the removal of contaminants of emerging concern #CECs from water streams

cutt.ly/PRISTINEnewsle...

PRISTINE LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · Dec 21 ...
 Do you know what #emergingcontaminants are? 😊

They are compounds of different origin and chemical nature disseminated in the environment, in really low concentrations

In #LIFEPRISTINE our objective is to remove this contaminants from water streams ✅

eurecat.org/portfolio-item...

LIFE PRISTINE @PRISTINE_EU · 16h

The #PRISTINE Integrated Solution is based on the synergistical combination of these technologies:

- ◆ Adsorbing capsules
- ◆ Hollow-fibre NF membranes
- ◆ Advanced Oxidation Processes #AOP UV-LED reactor
- ◆ #AI-based soft sensors

Know more in our web 📄

eurecat.org/en/portfolio-i...

ACCIONA and 9 others

Figure 17. First battery of tweets

4.3.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. The portal allows the user to create interest groups around specific initiatives or projects, ask or answer questions, post or search for jobs, etc.

At the beginning of the project, EUT created a LinkedIn page, which will allow to have a corporate timeline where the project and connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as connect and engage with cooperative connected automated mobility stakeholders.

The publication pace in LinkedIn will be less frequent than Twitter. Content will be based on project news, blog posts and reports/publications produced in the framework of the project or by trusted sources.

Figure 18. View of LinkedIn profile

4.3.2.1 Account strategy

The LinkedIn account will be managed by EUT. Bimonthly content plans will be produced to ensure a regular publication pace. Contents will include:

- Audiovisual and digital promotional materials
- Press releases produced
- News produced by project partners published in LIFE PRISTINE website.
- Specific information on the water technologies sector and emerging contaminants that can be of interest to the industrial community
- Participation in key fairs and congresses of the project topics
- Promotion of training activities, workshops and events for the industrial community.

All consortium partners will be able to propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed through this channel and can spread the word through their own corporate and personal channels by sharing the content published.

Publishing, as well as comments, answers and private messages will be managed manually, to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

The use of the hashtags is recommended (the same as defined in the Twitter strategy).

4.3.2.2 Analytics

Data on publications' impact will be retrieved from LinkedIn Analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

By the end of M5, the LIFE PRISTINE LinkedIn profile has 51 **followers**, **8 posts published** and **3,836 impressions**. (Data Analytics from October 2022 - M3 until December 2022 - M5).

4.3.3 *YouTube*

The European Commission has recommended the use of resources as the storytelling for putting objectives and results of the research projects closer to the general public. This narrative technique is based on the narrative of a story and it is used on marketing strategies to better reach users thanks to a character and a plot.

Following these recommendations, the videos produced within the project will be published in a **YouTube channel** and will be shared on the website and project's Twitter and LinkedIn for a broader impact.

On the other hand, the account will serve as a content **repository of all audiovisual content that may be produced during the project**.

Data on videos views and channels subscribers will be collected from YouTube analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Figure 19. View of YouTube channel

4.3.4 Awareness raising campaigns

Three awareness raising campaigns in social media are envisaged during the course of the project. These campaigns will include information about the presence of CECs in the environment and the efforts of the water sector towards their removal. They will also suggest simple gestures to reduce the emissions of CECs into the environment.

Additionally, the campaigns will also be promoted through ACC and LIFE PRISTINE project websites.

LIFE PRISTINE awareness raising campaigns	
Campaign 1	M18
Campaign 2	M30
Campaign 3	M42

Table 1. Awareness raising campaigns schedule

4.3.5 Partners channels

Each partner will convey LIFE PRISTINE news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published on <https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/life-pristine/> or in LIFE PRISTINE’s Twitter account.

LIFE PRISTINE’s partners impact in social media channels will reach more than **185K users on Twitter**, more than **252K on LinkedIn** and more than **41K Facebook** followers.

The corporate accounts to be used are:

PARTNER	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn	Instagram
ACC	N/A	@ACCIONA	http://www.linkedin.com/showcase/accionagua	N/A
EUT	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/	@Eurecat_news	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/	N/A
NXF	N/A	N/A	https://www.linkedin.com/company/nx-filtration/	N/A
ESAMUR	https://www.facebook.com/esamuraguas/	@ESAMUR_Aguas	https://www.linkedin.com/company/esamuraguas/	https://www.instagram.com/esamuraguas/
XYLEM	https://www.facebook.com/XylemIncorporated/	@Xylem	https://www.linkedin.com/company/xylem-inc/	https://www.instagram.com/xylem_inc/

Table 2. LIFE PRISTINE partners social media channels

4.3.6 Guidelines to publish about the project on social media

Partners are suggested to apply the following recommendations when communication about the project on social media:

- Use #LIFEPRISTINE #PRISTINE project hashtag or mention @PRISTINE_EU if you are using Twitter or tag the LinkedIn account (LIFE PRISTINE).
- Mention project partners to increase your reach.
- Share links to project website/materials.
- Communicate partners' role/task on the project.

Additionally, partners can also use the guidelines prepared for the project's accounts when publishing about the project in social media.

4.4 Promotional materials

4.4.1 General project materials

EUT is in charge of the creation of all visual material to support dissemination activities such as conferences, congresses, or project events. LIFE PRISTINE project will create communication

materials such as a **general brochure (M6)**, a **technical brochure (M25-36)** a **roll-up** and an **A1 poster**.

These materials will serve as the project’s business card and will be distributed as widely as possible, including the general public, conferences, workshops and other events, from the beginning of the project.

All materials will be stored digitally in the project’s internal repository and on the project’s website for broader dissemination. Promotional materials will be regularly updated according to the project’s developments.

4.4.1.1 Trifold

A trifold describing LIFE PRISTINE project was elaborated containing an introduction of the project, the main objectives, key outputs, the demonstration scenarios, a description of contaminants of emerging concerns and main objectives to be achieved, among other relevant information.

A more technical brochure is planned in the third year of the project, focused on tangible results and experiences from case studies.

Figure 20. View of LIFE PRISTINE tri-fold

4.4.1.2 Poster

An A1 poster, based on the main objectives of the project, the contaminants of emerging concern, and the PRISTINE Integrated Solution, was produced as a promotional material of the project.

Removing contaminants of emerging concern from water streams

Innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove emerging pollutants in water treatment systems

LIFE PRISTINE is postulated as a sustainable alternative to guarantee the elimination of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from the integral water cycle. To do so, LIFE PRISTINE integrates water treatment processes and digital tools based on artificial intelligence in a unique solution designed for the elimination CECs in drinking water and wastewater.

The integrated and versatile PRISTINE solution will be demonstrated in two operational environments, representing real water treatment plants, in order to facilitate subsequent full-scale implementation.

1 Encapsulated adsorbents

2 Hollow-fibre nanofiltration membranes

3 Advanced Oxidation UV-LED reactor

4 Artificial intelligence based soft sensors

PRISTINE Solution

The PRISTINE solution aims to remove CECs in a more sustainable and cost-effective way. Thereby CECs in the water environment shall not only be relocated into other media and waste streams, but the release of CECs to the water cycle shall be permanently reduced.

What are Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs)?

Contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) are compounds of different origin and chemical nature that are disseminated in the environment, in concentrations so low that they make their detection difficult. Relatively little is known in terms of their presence, impact and elimination.

LIFE PRISTINE will focus on perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), pesticides, pharmaceuticals and personal care products, toxins, antibiotic resistance genes and microplastics as the main families of emerging contaminants.

LIFE PRISTINE main goal is to eliminate emerging pollutants from the integral water cycle, one of the essential measures to promote high-quality water resources in the face of water scarcity, a problem that affects to more than 2.8 billion people around the world.

eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/life-pristine
 @PRISTINE_eu
 LIFE PRISTINE
lifepristineproject@gmail.com

Co-funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 21. View of LIFE PRISTINE poster

4.4.1.3 Rollup

A project rollup was produced to be used when attending events and/or to share through LIFE PRISTINE's communication channels.

PRiSTiNE

Innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove emerging pollutants in water treatment systems

Removing contaminants of emerging concern from water streams

- 1 Encapsulated adsorbents
- 2 Hollow fibre nanofiltration membranes
- 3 Advanced Oxidation UV-LED reactor
- 4 Artificial intelligence based soft sensors

PRiSTiNE

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eureca!.org/en/portfolio-items/life-pristine
 @PRISTINE_es
 LIFE-PRISTINE
 lifepristineproject@gmail.com

Figure 22. View of LIFE PRISTINE rollout

4.4.2 Audiovisual materials

The production of engaging videos is proposed to present the key aspects of the project. The videos produced within the project will be published on the LIFE PRISTINE website and social media channels, as well as in the YouTube channel.

These videos will summarise challenges of CECs, project’s objectives, proposed solutions through AI and expected results, showcasing images and end user testimonies with all success cases obtained during demos.

The production of other audiovisual materials will be evaluated among the consortium if any other opportunities arise. Partners will be able to propose other video topics and produce complementary videos on their contribution to the LIFE PRISTINE project.

Video	Objective	Month
1	Publicise the objectives of the project and the expected impact	M16
2	Share the assembly of the pilot plant and its installation in the demo site	M26
3	Disseminate the results of the project	M47

Table 3. Production of videos planning

4.5 Press releases

Press releases will be written and sent throughout the project focusing on the release of research results, project milestones, attendance at specialised events, conferences, etc.

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English for providing feedback (where appropriate), giving them the opportunity to adapt the documents in their corporate language and to circulate it among their regional media contacts.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented to a specific stakeholder group may be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator and Communication Leader (EUT).

In the framework of the project, a database with the contact details of partners’ communication officers will be created, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press release and increase the project’s impact across European media outlets.

4.5.1 Outlets of interest

During the project a **minimum of 4 informative publications are planned in trade magazines, such as the listed in table 5**. The schedule, partner responsible, and magazine selection, as well as the tracking media appearances, will be discussed in partners meetings.

As of M6, an interview has been carried out between Ana Jiménez-Banzo, LIFE PRISTINE coordinator, and the specialised outlet “Aguas Residuales”:

- [Ana Jiménez-Banzo, coordinadora del LIFE PRISTINE nos comenta todos los detalles de este proyecto sobre CEC](#)

The objective is for a wide range of readers to reach the project topics involved in academia, as well as industry. An initial list of European and global specialised media outlets identified as relevant to promote LIFE PRISTINE outputs include:

Outlet name	Website	Language
iAgua	https://www.iagua.es/	Spanish
RETEMA	https://www.retema.es/	Spanish
Aguas Residuales	https://www.aguasresiduales.info/	Spanish
FuturEnviro	https://futurenviro.es/	Spanish
DWA KA Korrespondenz Abwasser	http://de.dwa.de/de/ka-korrespondenz-abwasser-abfall.html	German
DVGW Publications	https://www.dvgw.de/leistungen/publikationen	German
Gwf Wasser/Abwasser	https://gwf-wasser.de/gwf-wasser-abwasser/	German
EUWID Wasser Abwasser	https://www.euwid-wasser.de/	German
Water Europe	https://watereurope.eu/news/	English
Water News Europe	https://www.waternewseurope.com/	English

Table 4. Specialised outlets of interest

4.5.2 Press release produced

During M1 - M6, LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination leader EUT produced **one press release** with general information about the project and its consortium which was distributed to all partners.

- Consortium press release: <https://eurecat.org/en/acciona-leads-an-initiative-to-eliminate-emerging-pollutants-in-the-end-to-end-water-cycle/>

Acciona leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in the end-to-end water cycle
Home / Projects / LIFE Pristine / Acciona leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in the end-to-end water cycle

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New smart mobility solutions to unlock connected and shared transport.
December 1st, 2022

Miliumverd innovates with Eurecat searching for sustainable packaging to commercialise its brand of Casoil oil.
November 18th, 2022

AETIB and Eurecat collaborate in the development of a training plan aimed at the tourism sector.
November 18th, 2022

Acciona leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in the end-to-end water cycle

- The LIFE PRISTINE project combines water treatment processes with artificial intelligence-based digital tools to develop a solution that removes emerging pollutants in the integrated water cycle. The integrated and versatile PRISTINE solution will be demonstrated in a representative full-scale operational environment.
- LIFE PRISTINE, with a budget of 4 million euros, also has the participation of Eurecat, NX Filtration, Xylem Servicios and the Entidad Regional de Saneamiento y Depuración de Aguas residuales de la región de Murcia (ESAMUR), as well as the support of the Consorcio de Aguas de Bilbao Bizkaia (CABB).

ACCIONA leads the European innovation project LIFE PRISTINE, whose objective is to eliminate emerging contaminants in the integral water cycle, one of the essential measures to promote alternative water resources in the face of water scarcity, which affects more than 2.8 billion people worldwide.

Many forums have alerted on the urgent need to take steps to protect water resources, mainly through a reduction in water consumption but also by promoting alternative resources through desalination or reuse. These non-conventional resources are essential to guarantee water

Figure 23. Press release published on the LIFE PRISTINE website

EUT wrote the first press release with the inputs of all the project’s partners and sent it to general media outlets as well as specialised magazine and journals.

Based on this press release, partners also adapted and/or translated their own versions.

- EUT (Catalan): [Eurecat participa en una iniciativa liderada per Acciona per a l’eliminació de contaminants emergents en el cicle integral de l’aigua](#)
- EUT (Spanish): [Eurecat participa en una iniciativa liderada por Acciona para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua](#)
- NXF (English): [NX Filtration part of ACCIONA-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources](#)
- ACC (Spanish): [ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua](#)

Eurecat participa en una iniciativa liderada per Acciona per a l'eliminació de contaminants emergents en el cicle integral de l'aigua

El centre tecnològic Eurecat participa en el projecte d'innovació europeu LIFE PRISTINE, liderat per ACCIONA, que té com a objectiu eliminar els contaminants emergents en el cicle integral de l'aigua, una de les mesures essencials per potenciar recursos hídrics alternatius davant de l'escassetat d'aigua, que afecta més de 2.800 milions de persones a tot el món.

Des de diferents fòrums s'està alertant de la necessitat urgent de prendre mesures per a la protecció dels recursos hídrics, tant mitjançant la reducció del consum d'aigua com la cerca de recursos hídrics alternatius a través de la dessalinització o la reutilització. Aquests recursos no convencionals resulten claus per garantir l'aigua necessària en sectors com l'agrícola, el consumidor més gran de la UE.

En aquest marc, un dels reptes a superar per afavorir la reutilització d'aigua és l'eliminació de contaminants emergents i microplàstics, substàncies d'origen antropogènic de difícil eliminació pels sistemes de depuració actuals, i que poden acabar en mars i rius, o fins i tot arribar a entrar a la cadena tròfica. Tot i estar presents en quantitats ínfimes, la seva persistència pot arribar a ocasionar riscos, motiu pel qual cada cop més s'incideix en la regulació de l'ús d'aquestes substàncies o en el desenvolupament de solucions per eliminar-les del medi ambient.

LIFE PRISTINE es postula com una alternativa sostenible per garantir l'eliminació de contaminants emergents (+80%) al cicle integral de l'aigua, anant més enllà dels límits establerts per la Directiva d'aigua per al consum humà (Directiva 2020/2184/CE) i el nou reglament europeu relatiu als requisits mínims per a la reutilització de l'aigua (Reglament (UE) 2020/741). LIFE-PRISTINE se centra en contaminants emergents de tipus PFAS (polifluoroalquilis, relacionats amb retardants de flama), pesticides, productes farmacèutics i de cura personal, toxines, gens de resistència a antibiòtics i microplàstics. El projecte contribuirà al reforç de la cooperació europea i regional i a la reutilització d'aigua amb les

Figure 24. Part of the press release produced by EUT

Enschede, the Netherlands, 11 October 2022

NX Filtration part of ACCIONA-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources

NX Filtration, the global provider of breakthrough direct nanofiltration technology for pure and affordable water, announces its participation in the European innovation project LIFE PRISTINE, led by ACCIONA S.A. The project's objective is to eliminate emerging contaminants in the integral water cycle, one of the essential measures to promote alternative water resources in the face of water scarcity, which affects more than 2.8 billion people worldwide.

- The LIFE PRISTINE project has a budget of 4 million euros and is coordinated by ACCIONA, the Spanish sustainable infrastructure solutions group. Next to ACCIONA and NX Filtration, project partners include Eurecat, Xylem Services, the Regional Entity for Wastewater Sanitation and Treatment of the Murcia Region (ESAMUR) and the water utility provider Bilbao Bizkaia Water Consortium (CABB).

- The LIFE PRISTINE project combines water treatment processes, including NX Filtration's hollow fiber nanofiltration membranes, with artificial intelligence-based digital tools to develop a solution that removes emerging pollutants in the integrated water cycle. The integrated and versatile PRISTINE solution will be demonstrated in a representative full-scale operational environment.

Figure 25. Part of the press release produced by NXF

ACCIONA / ACTUALIDAD / ARTICULOS ← Volver

ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua

05 OCTUBRE, 2022

- El proyecto LIFE PRISTINE combina procesos de tratamiento de agua con herramientas digitales basadas en inteligencia artificial para desarrollar una solución que elimine los contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua. La solución PRISTINE, integrada y versátil, será demostrada en un entorno operativo representativo de escala real.
- LIFE PRISTINE, cuyo presupuesto asciende a 4 millones de euros, cuenta también con la participación de Eurecat, NX Filtration, Xylem Servicios y la Entidad Regional de Saneamiento y Depuración de Aguas residuales de la región de Murcia (ESAMUR), además del apoyo del Consorcio de Aguas de Bilbao Bizkaia (CABB).

ACCIONA liderará el proyecto de innovación europeo LIFE PRISTINE, cuyo objetivo es eliminar los contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua, una de las medidas esenciales para potenciar recursos hídricos alternativos frente a la escasez de agua, que afecta a más de 2.800 millones de personas en todo el mundo.

Desde distintos foros se está alertando de la necesidad urgente de tomar medidas para la protección de los recursos hídricos, tanto mediante la reducción del consumo de agua como la búsqueda de recursos hídricos alternativos a través de la desalinización o la reutilización. Estos recursos no convencionales resultan claves para garantizar el agua necesaria en sectores como el agrícola, el mayor consumidor de la UE.

En este marco, uno de los retos a superar para favorecer la reutilización de agua es la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes y microplásticos, sustancias de origen antropogénico de difícil eliminación por los actuales sistemas de depuración, y que pueden acabar en mares y ríos, o incluso llegar a entrar en la cadena trófica. Pese a estar presentes en cantidades ínfimas, su persistencia puede llegar a ocasionar riesgos, motivo por el cual cada vez más se incide en la regulación del uso de estas sustancias o en el desarrollo de soluciones para su

Figure 26. Part of the press release produced by ACC

4.5.3 Media impacts

As result of this action, LIFE PRISTINE project was featured in a total of **10 specialised media outlets** at local, regional, and national level.

DATE	MEDIA	TITLE	TYPE	LANGUAGE	LINK
13/10/22	Filtration + Separation	NX Filtration joins European initiative to eliminate	Online	English	Link

		emerging pollutants from water sources			
12/10/22	Water & Wastewater Asia	NX Filtration to be part of Acciona-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources	Online	English	Link
11/10/22	Obras Urbanas	Iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
09/10/22	Aqua Tech	EU COLLABORATION LINKS MEMBRANES & AI TO TARGET EMERGING POLLUTANTS	Online	English	Link
07/10/22	TecnoAqua	Acciona lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
06/10/22	FuturENVIRO	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
06/10/22	Aguasresiduales.info	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de Contaminantes Emergentes en el Ciclo Integral del Agua	Online	Spanish	Link
05/10/22	Smart Water Magazine	ACCIONA leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in end-to-end water cycle	Online	English	Link
05/10/22	iAgua	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
05/10/22	Retema	ACCIONA lidera LIFE PRISTINE para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link

Table 5. LIFE PRISTINE media impacts

4.5.4 Press release plan

A total of 8 press releases or news for the media are planned throughout the project.

LIFE PRISTINE press release plan		Partners responsible
M3	1 st press release of the project - DONE	EUT, ACC, distributed in partners regions
M15	Results of the analytical campaign for demo sites characterisation	EUT, ACC, ESAMUR
M18	Development and fine-tuning of individual technologies	EUT, ACC, NXF, XYL
M24	Development of process models and Decision Support System	EUT, ACC
M35	Demonstration of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution in a wastewater treatment real scenario	ALL
M47	Demonstration of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution in a drinking water treatment real scenario	ALL
M48	Final project results	EUT, ACC, distributed in partners regions
MXX	Participation in an important event	TBD

Table 6. LIFE PRISTINE press release plan

4.6 Newsletters

News and updated of the project will be distributed via newsletters to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the latest project’s developments.

The **database of subscribers will be built during the whole project**, putting the main efforts during the first months of the project to have an acceptable number of subscribers for the first release.

Four newsletters will be issued:

LIFE PRISTINE newsletters schedule	
1 st Newsletter	M12
2 nd Newsletter	M24
3 rd Newsletter	M36
4 th Newsletter	M48

Table 7. Newsletter schedule

The LIFE PRISTINE newsletter will be disseminated via links on social media, direct ad hoc emails to professional contacts of the consortium partners and via browsing the LIFE PRISTINE website, where all newsletter issues will be stored.

Furthermore, information about LIFE PRISTINE project will be included to partners' newsletters or corporate publications, such as EUT's monthly corporate newsletter addressed to external audience, with more than 15,000 subscribers.

4.6.1 Platform

EUT proposes Mailchimp as the email platform to be used for the newsletter design, sending and stats monitoring. Mailchimp allows to easily create newsletters of varying types and then provides simple options for sharing them on social networks such as Twitter or Facebook.

4.6.2 Audience

EUT has decided to create and build the LIFE PRISTINE's Community of Interest. The database of subscribers will be built during the whole project and will be gained progressively via a signup form published on the website homepage and promoted via social media channels, as well as partners' channels.

This signup form complies with GDPR, linking to the project's privacy policy and informing the user about its right to cancel the subscription at any time.

EUT proposes Mailchimp as the email platform to be used for sending the updated and specific information. Subscriptions and unsubscribes are managed automatically via Mailchimp. Data collected through the signup form will be used for the exclusive purpose of sending subscribers information related to the project and will never be passed to third-party companies, unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

PRISTINE

Subscribe now to be updated on LIFE PRISTINE project developments, latest news and events. By subscribing to our community of interest you will be emailed once a year with information on LIFE PRISTINE results in a newsletter form.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will use the information you provide on this form according to the [Data Treatment Information](#).

First Name

Last Name

Email Address

I wish to receive information on:

LIFE PRISTINE project developments

Other related projects participated / coordinated by Eurecat

Privacy Policy Information

Your subscription shall be treated according to the Privacy Information above mentioned. You may consult it through the link at beginning of the form.

I have read and I accept the privacy policy and the data treatment information

You can unsubscribe at any time by clicking the link in the footer of our emails. For information about our privacy practices, please visit our website.

 We use Mailchimp as our marketing platform. By clicking below to subscribe, you acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing. [Learn more about Mailchimp's privacy practices here.](#)

Figure 27. Community of interest signup form

4.6.3 Content

EUT will be responsible for the content of newsletters issues, with the contribution of all partners. Before every publication, partners will be contacted for inputs (e.g. information on project tasks or events where the project was presented).

The content of the newsletters will follow project milestones. Every issue will include the appropriate references to the LIFE Programme and contact details (email and link to the website and social media).

4.6.4 Analytics

Newsletter analytics, such as open rate or click through rate, will be **extracted through Mailchimp**. Statistics will be checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and will be analysed in order to see which articles worked best and be able to improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

5 PRISTINE Dissemination Plan (PDP)

5.1 Exhibitions, fairs and congresses

Participation in national and international conferences and trade shows is essential in order to reach large industrial and scientific sectors. A wide range of venues are suitable for the exhibition and publication of the LIFE PRISTINE results, relating to project topics.

Oral presentations, exhibitions of the project outputs and/or distribution of promotional material is expected.

Dissemination will mainly focus on partners countries (Spain, Germany, and the Netherlands) but partners will also consider attending events taking place in other European countries and across the EU borders, targeting communities strongly related to the project objectives, certainly including academia and the water sector.

Participation to academic and industrial events will be discussed during WP-leaders’ meetings. An Excel file allocated in Teams folder is available for partners to note their planned activities or the identification of any events of interest.

A non-exhaustive list of events already identified as relevant to continue disseminating LIFE PRISTINE activities and outcomes are presented in table 9. The list will be periodically updated by partners.

Name	Typology	Dates next edition	City	Country
Singapore International Water Week	Congress	TBD	Singapore	Singapore
European Research and Innovation Days	EU Event	TBD	TBD	TBD
Membrane Technology	Conference & exposition	February 2023	Knoxville	United States
IEEXPo	Trade fair	April 2023	Shanghai	China
AEDyR International Congress	Congress	June 2023	Granada	Spain
Water Innovation Europe	EU Event	June 2023	Brussels	Belgium
EU Green Week	EU Event	June 2023	Brussels	Belgium
Stockholm Water Week	Congress	August 2023	Stockholm	Sweden
Instrumentation Control and Automaton	Conference	August 2023	Jakarta	Indonesia
WEFTEC	Exhibition & Conference	October 2023	Chicago	United States
Aqua Tech	Exhibition	November 2023	Amsterdam	The Netherlands
SETAC Europe	Conference	May 2024	Sevilla	Spain
IFAT	Trade fair	May 2024	Munchen	Germany
World Water Congress	Congress & Exhibition	August 2024	Toronto	Canada

Table 8. Identified list of conferences, fairs and exhibitions of interest

5.1.1 Attended dissemination events

Up to M6, partners have disseminated LIFE PRISTINE in one event:

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	LOCATION	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION
November 16-19, 2022	3 rd Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals	Industry Community	Valencia, Spani	ACCIONA	Presentation of the LIFE PRISTINE project, focusing on the project's objectives, technology and demonstration scenarios MORE INFO

Table 9. Attended dissemination events

5.1.2 Planned dissemination events

Partners have planned the following dissemination activities:

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	LOCATION	PARTNER	TYPE OF DISSEMINATION
June 13-15, 2023	XIII AEDYR International Congress	Industry Community	Granada, Spain	ACC	Presentation of the LIFE PRISTINE project
February 1, 2023	ISLE-iAgua Utilities Webinar Series	Industry community	Online	ACC	Presentation of the LIFE PRISTINE project
June 26-29, 2023	ecoSTP-23	Industry Community	Girona, Spain	ACC	Presentation of the LIFE PRISTINE project

Table 10. Planned dissemination events

5.2 Scientific publications

Reports or outcomes resulting from the project activities will be published in scientific journals related to the project's fields. During the project period **at least four publications in international journals are planned.**

As the appearance of results and technical maturity is not yet exactly plannable, the schedule of these actions is flexible being controlled by EUT and follows the work package plan.

During the periodic meetings of the WP leaders relevant results will be discussed and partners, timing set and journals chosen. The type of journals shall be related to the matter of results, such as Environmental Science and Technology or Water Practice and Technology IWA Publishing.

Any report or results from the project activities will be made available through public access repositories once exploitation opportunities were safeguarded in terms of confidentiality and IP protection. Examples of public access repositories are:

- **OpenAire** (www.openaire.eu). This platform permits to make journals, project data and deliverables and research studies available for free. It actuates as a document repository where an organisation can create its own repository and the researcher can upload its studies.
- **Zenodo** (<http://zenodo.org>). Similarly, this portal permits to share scientific publications using creative commons licenses.

Before any publication of LIFE PRISTINE results, partners will contact the project coordinator, the Dissemination Manager and Exploitation Manager to verify if these do not infringer IP rights.

Before submitting any paper for publication, it is necessary to inform the consortium and show what is going to be presented publicly, so every partner agree on the content.

Each partner will ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications submitted and published via **gold open access whenever available** (provided via the published when an article is published) and/or **green open access** via an online repository to ensure a long-term preservation and availability of the publication.

When publishing scientific papers in open access repositories, the EC requires the following bibliographic metadata to identify the publication:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “LIFE Programme”.
- The name of the action, acronym of grant number.
- The publication date, length and embargo period if applicable.
- A persistent identifier.

The Project Coordinator will be responsible for final decisions regarding open access publications. Although gold open access options will be preferred, partners have a small budgetary allocation to ensure open access in case journals’ policies are restrictive.

An initial list of open-access journals of interest for publishing LIFE PRISTINE results has been defined, as follows:

Journal name	Link
Environmental Science and Technology	https://pubs.acs.org/journal/esthag
Environmental Modelling and Software	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/environmental-modelling-and-software
Journal of Hazardous Materials	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-hazardous-materials
Environmental Pollution	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/environmental-pollution

<i>Chemosphere</i>	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/chemosphere
<i>Ozone Science & Engineering</i>	https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/bose20
<i>Water Practice and Technology IWA Publishing</i>	https://iwaponline.com/wpt

Table 11. Open-access journals of interest

On the other hand, partners will consider the submission of papers to the **Open Research Europe**, an innovative open access publishing platform offering rapid publication and open peer review.

5.3 Networking activities

Wide and transversal dissemination of project activities and results is crucial to maximize impact and level of engagement across all identified stakeholders.

For this purpose, this task will involve participation, the setting up and organisation of project meetings, technical forums/workshops and conferences not only to raise awareness of LIFE PRISTINE, but also create a link with emerging European, regional and national initiatives, ensuring collaboration with them to increase project’s long-term sustainability.

5.3.1 Workshops

Attending and organizing workshops has been recognized as a key activity to share the project’s results and create synergies among other similar projects, potential customers and partners, as well as open up the project’s results to the specialized audience interested in the project’s innovative technology.

Partners agreed on organizing **2 workshops during the project’s last year** to disseminate the project results at important events in the industrial sector. Partners will be responsible to present the project outputs and share the know-how generated during the project with the academic/scientific and industrial community.

The main objectives of the workshops are:

- To introduce potential end-users with the technology and expected benefits.
- To receive feedback from the potential end-users in order to increase its replicability and possible success on the market.
- To learn from the recommendations from the potential end-users and accelerate take-ups of the new technology.

5.3.2 Related project exchanges

Connections with other projects, initiatives and knowledge hubs with complementary interests will be sought at national, EU and international level with the aim of enhancing synergies while avoiding duplication of efforts in the dissemination of results.

Partnering with other projects and initiatives will allow to join efforts and also have a stronger voice when communicating with target audiences.

Additionally, partners will actively interact with the initiatives promoted by these groups and contribute with content on the project to feed associations’ newsletters and publications, when possible. A total of 8 networking meetings during the project are envisaged.

Some of the LIFE PRISTINE sister projects and initiatives identified to date, dealing with increasing efficiency of CECs removal, are listed in table 13.

LIFE PRISTINE sister projects	
LIFE SOuRCE (ending 2025)	The objective is to demonstrate an innovative cost-efficient and versatile remediation solution for PFAS contaminated groundwater.
LIFE PHOENIX (ending 2024)	LIFE-PHOENIX is aimed at developing low-cost innovative technologies for WW agricultural reuse
SCENARIOS H2020 (ending 2025)	The objective is to demonstrate a comprehensive set of technological solutions to address the detection, (bio)monitoring, long-term toxicity, risk assessment, pollution control and remediation of PFAs as a test bed for zero pollution ambition from refractory and mobile organic chemicals.
PANI WATER H2020 (ending 2023)	The objective is to develop, deploy and validate in the field six prototypes for the removal of contaminants, including CECs, from WW and DW.
ECO-SOS H2020 (ending 2023)	The project will develop hybrid soft sensors for on-line monitoring of contaminants of emerging concern in water.
PROMISCES H2020 (ending 2025)	The objective is to develop new analytical methods and toxicological tools to provide data on persistent mobile (PM) substances (i.e., PFAS) in the soil-sediment-water system.

Table 12. LIFE PRISTINE sister projects

5.3.3 Local info-days

A local info-day will be celebrated on each demonstration site where the LIFE PRISTINE Pilot Plant will be installed. The objective of these events is to present project progress and achievement to local stakeholders, gathering specific inputs to create enabling framework for LIFE PRISTINE.

LIFE PRISTINE local info-days	
WWTP	M35
DWTP	M46

Table 13. Local info-days schedule

5.3.4 Final event

A final event will be organized at the end of the project for a publicly presentation of the project results (M48) among key stakeholders (academic/scientific and industrial community). Partners will decide whether hosting the event in one of the consortium countries or within a key congress/conference (see Table 9).

Partners aim at gathering about 200 attendees, including members from key specialised media outlets. The event will be open to all interested parties and promoted throughout LIFE PRISTINE and partners communication channels, but partners will also send private invitations to key contacts in their portfolio. EUT will be the main responsible partners for the organization of the event, which will include also the contribution of all partners.

6 Communication and Dissemination Management

6.1 Monitoring and reporting

6.1.1 Activities reporting

Following a specific methodology applied to all European Projects, EUT Research Communication Office has prepared an Excel file to register all dissemination and communication activities done by partners during project execution.

This file, located in the Microsoft Teams online repository is available to all partners (WP8 - Communication and raise awareness - 00_Reporting - KPI_Reporting_PRISTINE) contains, among others, a description of dissemination activity, type and size of audience, date and location, partner/s involved and feedback received, among others.

LIFE PRISTINE Dissemination activities								
Dissemination action	Status	Dates	Event name	Type of audience	Size of audience	Place	Partner	Website
Participation to a Congress / Exhibition	Attended	October 17, 2022	Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals (IWA)	Industry Community	TBD	Valencia, Spain	ACC	https://www.ywsp-spain.es/
Participation to a Congress / Exhibition	Abstract submitted	June 13-15, 2023	XIII AEDYR International Congress	Industry Community	TBD	Granada, Spain	ACC	https://aedyr.com/congres

Figure 28. View of reporting activities table

Separately, a folder titled “Events” has been created. After a dissemination event takes place (organized or attended by LIFE PRISTINE project partners), a folder with the name of the event will be created inside the “Events” folder with the dissemination materials presented (poster, presentation, promotional materials, etc.) and some photographic evidence on the dissemination action.

Nombre	Modificado	Modificado por
00_Reporting	2 de noviembre	Iván García Cerdà
Events	Hace unos segundos	Iván García Cerdà
Free-to-use images	10 de octubre	Iván García Cerdà
Logo	25 de octubre	Iván García Cerdà
Press releases	7 de octubre	Iván García Cerdà
Templates	10 de octubre	Iván García Cerdà
Visual identity guidebook	10 de octubre	Iván García Cerdà

Figure 29. View of the “Events” folder within Microsoft Teams

6.1.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

KPIs have been assigned to several communication and dissemination activities planned in the project to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project. Progress regarding project KPIs will be reported in WP8 upcoming deliverables, project meetings and project review reports. The main KPIs established are listed in Table 1.

Project output (KPI)	Target Group	Objective	KPI Targets
Project logo, visuals, presentation templates	All	Creating a common visual identity	N.A.
Interactive digital platform (# of total website visits by the end of the project)	All	Main entry point to the project, repository of news and public contents	10,000
Social Media (# of Twitter and LinkedIn followers) (# of tweets and LinkedIn posts)	All	Interaction and engagement with online communities. Managed by local partners in local languages	500 250
Project Brochures / Leaflets (# of brochures created) (# of brochures / leaflets distributed)	All	Communication materials to be distributed at events	2 500
Media coverage (# of press releases / articles)	All	Project related news for the media.	8
Social awareness campaigns (# of released campaigns)	All	Social media campaigns to inform about CECs origin, impact, and treatment	3
Annual Newsletter (# of newsletters) (# of digital subscribers)	All	These newsletters may include interviews and other relevant related articles.	4 200
Videos (# of project videos) (# of video views)	All	Short videos presenting the project features	2 2,000
Informative publications	All	Independent articles about the project published in trade magazines focusing on either: overview of the	4

(# of informative articles)		project, advantages of proposed solutions, etc.	
Policy related events			
(# of European and national/regional event participation)	Policy actors & decision makers	Participation in future policy making improvement to regulate CECs.	3
Scientific Conferences	Policy actors and decision makers, Industry (Water utilities, Technology providers), Research & Academia	Participation in events presenting the project	4
(# of conference publications)			
EU Events, Trade Fairs, Projects & Workshops			
(# of events)			4
(# of project workshops)	Policy actors and decision makers, Industry, Research & Academia	Participation in events presenting the project	1
(# audience reached through the participation in conferences)			---
(# of participants in organised events)			50
International Journals	Policy actors and decision makers, Industry (Water utilities, Technology providers), Research & Academia	Presentation of project results	4
(# of journal publications)			
Related Project Exchanges	Industry (Water utilities, Technology providers), Research & Academia	Networking with other projects to explore synergies and lessons learnt	8
(# of networking meetings together)			
Final Event	All	Raise awareness of the project and its results	200
(# of attendees)			

Table 14. Communication & Dissemination KPIs

6.1.3 KPIs reporting

Progress until the end of the project will be reported in two updates of this deliverable, scheduled for M23 and M48, as well as in interim progress reports.

In addition, to facilitate the reporting, an Excel file has been prepared to record the monthly KPIs progress. The file, stored in the WP8 folder in the Microsoft Teams online repository, contains different tabs, including:

- **Web and Social Media:** to report progress on project and partners channels

KPIs LIFE PRISTINE digital channels						
	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	
Twitter corporate account						
Followers	N/A	N/A	0	19	19	
New Followers	N/A	N/A	0	19	0	
Total Tweets	N/A	N/A	1	8	11	
New Tweets	N/A	N/A	1	7	3	
Twitter Impressions	N/A	N/A	204	719	378	
Mentions	N/A	N/A	0	3	0	
Likes on Tweets	N/A	N/A	2	6	5	
Retweets	N/A	N/A	2	2	0	
Twitter partners' account						
ACC						
EUT						
NXF						
ESAMUR						
XYLEM						
TOTAL (Aggregate)						
Tweets	N/A	N/A	0	0	0	
Likes	N/A	N/A	0	0	0	
Retweets	N/A	N/A	0	0	0	
Replies	N/A	N/A	0	0	0	
LinkedIn corporate account						
Followers	N/A	N/A	18	48	51	
New Followers	N/A	N/A	18	30	3	
Total Posts	N/A	N/A	1	5	8	
New Posts	N/A	N/A	1	4	3	
Likes / Reactions	N/A	N/A	27	77	24	
Impressions	N/A	N/A	657	2577	602	
Shares	N/A	N/A	7	7	2	

Figure 30. View of the table to report digital channels KPIs

- **Scientific papers:** for tracking on-going and published papers

